

Triterpene acids from the gum-resin of *Shorea robusta*

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Chemical analysis of the gum-resin of *Shorea robusta* revealed the presence of three triterpenoids 11-oxoasiatic acid (1), dryobalanolide (2) and asiatic acid (3) which were isolated as their triacetates 1a, 2a and 3a respectively. Their ¹³C nmr spectral data are reported.

Shorea robusta Gaertn.f., commonly known as *shal* in Bengal, has been found to be beneficial in haemorrhagic diseases and fever. The stem-bark (exuded resin) finds applications¹ as astringent, antidiarrhoeal and antidysenteric. Previous investigation of this species by other workers culminated in the isolation of a number of chemical constituents¹. We had earlier reported² the isolation and characterisation of an interesting polyphenolic compound, shoreaphenol from the bark of the plant. Present chemical analysis of the gum-resin revealed the presence of 11-oxoasiatic acid (1)³, dryobalanolide (2)³ and asiatic acid (3)⁴, isolated as their triacetates 1a, 2a and 3a. The ¹³C nmr spectral data of these compounds which constitute their first occurrence in this species, are being reported for the

first time.

Results and Discussion

The concentrated chloroform extract of the marc left after digestion of the gum-resin with ether was chromatographed over silica gel and the column was eluted with solvents of increasing polarity. Hexane-acetone (1 : 1 to 3 : 7) eluates on repeated column chromatography over Si-gel afforded a compound on elution with hexane-acetone (1 : 1) mixture. This compound resisted all attempts of purification (column) and crystallisation. It was, therefore, acetylated (Ac₂O/Py) to yield 11-oxoasiatic acid triacetate³ (≡ 2α, 3β, 23-triacetoxy-11-oxo-urs-12-en-28-oic acid). Its identity was indicated from uv, ir and ¹³C nmr spectral

data³ and was confirmed from detailed analysis of its ¹³C nmr spectral data (vide Experimental).

Earlier hexane-acetone (3 : 2 to 1 : 1) eluates of the original column on repeated chromatography using hexane-acetone (7 : 3) as eluent furnished a product containing at least two components as revealed from tlc. It was, therefore, acetylated (Ac₂O/Py) and the acetylated product on chromatographic resolution over Si-gel afforded dryobalanolide triacetate³ (2a) in the earlier fractions of petrol-acetone (17 : 3) eluates while the latter fractions gave asiatic acid triacetate⁴ (3a). The identity of both the compounds was confirmed by their ¹³C nmr spectral data (vide Experimental). Biogenetically 2 could be generated from 11-hydroxyursolic acid derivative through 13,28-lactonisation causing shift of the double bond from Δ¹²- to Δ¹¹-position with concomitant expulsion of 11-hydroxyl group.

Compound 3a showed the presence of a tri-substituted double bond (125.3, d, C-12; 138.0, s, C-13) and a carboxylic acid group (183.3, s, C-28). The ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectral data of 3a were essentially similar to those of 1a except that the former contained an unconjugated double bond as in urs-12-ene series of triterpenoids instead of a conjugated ketone system as in 1a. This led to the structure 3a for the triterpenoid triacetate and thence to 3 for the natural product.

Experimental

Plant material was collected locally and identified⁵, and a voucher specimen has been deposited at Regional Research Institute (Ay.), Calcutta. M.ps. are uncorrected. ¹H nmr (360 MHz) and ¹³C nmr (90 MHz) spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded with reference to TMS or CHCl₃ at δ 7.26. Silica gel (B.D.H., 60–120 mesh) and silica gel (Merck) were used for cc and tlc respectively. Samples were routinely dried over P₂O₅ for 24 h.

11-Oxoasiatic acid triacetate (1a): The gum-resin (10 g) of *S. robusta* was percolated with solvent ether. The marc left after extraction with ether was kept soaked in CHCl₃. The concentrated CHCl₃ extract was chromato-

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graphed over Si-gel and the column was eluted with solvents of increasing polarity.

Hexane : Me₂CO (1 : 1 to 3 : 7) eluates on repeated column chromatography over Si-gel yielded a material on elution with a mixture of hexane-Me₂CO (1 : 1) [*R_f* 0.47 (petrol : Me₂CO, 1 : 3)]. It was acetylated with Ac₂O/Py by heating on a water-bath. Usual work-up of the reaction mixture furnished a crude residue which was chromatographed over Si-gel using the same solvent elution (petrol : Me₂CO, 9 : 1) technique. Collections were 10 ml each. Fractions (15–24) gave 11-oxoasiatic acid triacetate (**1a**), *R_f* 0.31 (petrol : Me₂CO, 7 : 3); λ_{max} (EtOH) 253.5 (log ε 4.03); ν_{max} (KBr) 1670 (cyclohexenone), 1743, 1750, 1245, 1265 (acetoxo), 1738 (COOH) cm⁻¹; ¹³C nmr δ 44.1 (C-1), 68.9 (C-2), 74.8 (C-3), 37.6 (C-4), 47.3 (C-5), 17.0 (C-6), 32.4 (C-7), 41.9 (C-8), 61.0 (C-9), 43.7 (C-10), 199.0 (C-11), 130.6 (C-12), 163.0 (C-13), 44.6 (C-14), 28.2 (C-15), 23.5 (C-16), 47.4 (C-17), 52.4 (C-18), 38.5 (C-19), 38.5 (C-20), 30.2 (C-21), 35.9 (C-22), 65.2 (C-23), 13.8 (C-24), 16.9 (C-25), 17.7 (C-26), 19.0 (C-27), 182.7 (C-28), 20.8 (C-29), 21.0 (C-30) and 170.8, 170.5, 170.2, 20.9, 20.9, 20.9 for carbon signals of acetoxy groups.

Dryobalanolide triacetate (2a) and asiatic acid triacetate (3a) : Hexane-Me₂CO (3 : 2 to 1 : 1) eluates of the original column on repeated column chromatography gave a crude product when the column was eluted with hexane-Me₂CO (7 : 3) mixture. This material was found to contain more than one compound on tlc and could not be purified by column chromatography or crystallisation. It was then acetylated with Ac₂O/Py by heating on a water-bath for 1 h. After usual work-up the reaction product was chromatographed over Si-gel using the same solvent (petrol-Me₂CO, 17 : 3) elution technique. Collections were 20 ml each. Fractions (11–15) on concentration and crystallisation from petrol-Me₂CO mixture yielded dryobalanolide triacetate (**2a**), *R_f* 0.24 (petrol : Me₂CO, 4 : 1), 0.23 (petrol : ether, 7 : 3); ν_{max} (KBr) 1785 (γ-lactone), 1762, 1275, 1255 (acetoxo) cm⁻¹; ¹³C nmr δ 43.4 (C-1), 69.6 (C-2), 74.6 (C-3), 41.9 (C-4), 47.4 (C-5), 17.3 (C-6),

31.2 (C-7), 41.7 (C-8), 60.5 (C-9), 37.2 (C-10), 132.3 (C-11), 129.5 (C-12), 89.2 (C-13), 41.9 (C-14), 25.5 (C-15), 22.7 (C-16), 45.0 (C-17), 52.9 (C-18), 40.2 (C-19), 38.1 (C-20), 30.7 (C-21), 30.8 (C-22), 65.1 (C-23), 13.3 (C-24), 16.1 (C-25), 17.8 (C-26), 19.3 (C-27), 179.6 (C-28), 18.8 (C-29), 19.1 (C-30) and 170.8, 170.4, 170.3, 21.0, 20.9, 20.7 for carbon signals of acetoxy groups.

Fractions (17–19) furnished **3a**, C₃₆H₅₄O₈ (from CMR and DEPT), m.p. 140–42°; *R_f* 0.21 (petrol : Me₂CO, 4 : 1), 0.21 (petrol : ether, 7 : 3); ν_{max} (KBr) 1725 (COOH), 1760, 1772, 1258 (OCOCH₃) cm⁻¹; ¹³C nmr δ 43.7 (C-1), 69.9 (C-2), 74.8 (C-3), 41.9 (C-4), 47.5 (C-5), 17.9 (C-6), 32.4 (C-7), 39.5 (C-8), 47.6 (C-9), 37.8 (C-10), 23.3 (C-11), 125.3 (C-12), 138.0 (C-13), 41.9 (C-14), 27.9 (C-15), 24.0 (C-16), 47.9 (C-17), 52.5 (C-18), 39.0 (C-19), 38.8 (C-20), 30.6 (C-21), 36.6 (C-22), 65.3 (C-23), 13.9 (C-24), 16.9 (C-25), 17.0 (C-26), 23.4 (C-27), 183.3 (C-28), 17.0 (C-29), 21.2 (C-30) and 170.9, 170.5, 170.4, 20.9, 20.8, 21.1 for carbon signals of acetoxy groups.

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